

Ways to teach students to read quickly without errors

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bolalarni qanday tez o‘qishga o‘rgatish va hatosiz o‘qish usullari va yo‘llari haqida so‘z boradi .

Kalit so‘zlar: Tez o‘qish, intellektual faoliyat, suhbat, tinglash, aqliy faoliyat.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается о том, как научить детей читать быстро и как читать без ошибок.

Ключевые слова: скорочтение, интеллектуальная деятельность, беседа, аудирование, мыслительная деятельность.

Abstract: This article talks about how to teach children to read quickly and how to read without mistakes

Key words: Quick reading, intellectual activity, conversation, listening, mental activity.

Educators and psychologists say that children who barely learn to read in elementary school are getting worse and worse by the seventh or eighth grade. The slowness of the reading process, the lack of interest in reading leads to a slowdown in intellectual activity. Guys, read the condition of the task, train more slowly, forget its essence before proceeding with the implementation. Many terms and concepts that they should be aware of at this age are simply unknown and

uninteresting. It is no secret that a passion for reading, a strong interest in reading, is formed in the family and its basis is the child's habit of reading.

If a child grows and develops in an environment where talking, listening, reading are the norm of everyday life, he is also interested in meaningful and versatile information at school, which can be obtained mainly from books. He becomes an avid reader.

Experience shows that students who perform poorly do not do well in middle and high school, where learning material is multiplied many times over. In addition, reading improves working memory and attention span, on which mental activity depends. The development process also depends on reading speed. As a rule, students who read a lot learn quickly. Reading improves memory and attention. These two indicators, in turn, depend on mental activity. Sometimes abilities and thinking contradict each other. This is a common mistake. Reading skills should be formed in elementary school.

How can we as teachers help our children?

Let's analyze the norm of reading technique in the primary grades. It is known that the reading rate is at least 90 words per minute for students entering the 5th grade, and 120 words per minute at the beginning of the 5th grade. Where can a child get 30 words for the summer? This is a big problem for children with learning difficulties.

This also does not correspond to the optimal speed of conversational speech, and therefore the standard can be considered too low.

Working on reading technique is a long process and not always attractive for children. However, it would be difficult to teach in a high school without simple reading techniques.

1. Frequency of exercise. It's not the length of the workout that matters, but the frequency of the workout. The memory of a person is arranged in such a way that he remembers not what is always before his eyes, but what flickers: that is, not that. There is something to scratch and remember. Therefore, if we want to master some skills, bring them to automatism, mastery, then it is better to do short parts, but with greater frequency. In this regard, learning to read at home should be carried out in three to four sessions.

2. Reading a book before bed gives good results. The fact is that the last events of the day are recorded by emotional memory, and during those hours when a person sleeps, he is under their influence. Remember, children tell him a story before going to bed. Vivid impressions of an interesting book before going to bed will increase the taste of reading.

3. If the child does not like to read, then you need a soft reading mode. In fact, if a child does not like to read, then it is difficult for him to read. In soft reading mode, the child reads 1-2 lines and then takes a short break. If a child watches films, this mode is acquired automatically: he read two lines under the frame, looked at the picture - he rested. The next frame - read two more lines, then looked at the picture. This method is ideal for children who don't want to read.

4. Reading "Villab" also gives good results. In the usual method, the teacher

conducts conversations with more than 10 students in each lesson. In addition, each of them exercises for 1-2 minutes. During reading, if all students read aloud at the same time, each at their own pace for 5 minutes, so as not to disturb their peers, the time of the simulator increases dramatically.

5. Such a picture can be observed. Children's sentence of 6-8 words. They read up to the third or fourth word and forget the first. Therefore, he cannot link all the words together. In this case, it is necessary to develop working memory. I will do this with the help of visual dictations, the texts of which were developed and proposed by Professor I. T. Fedorenko. An indispensable condition for conducting visual dictations that develop working memory is their daily implementation. Usually the first successes appear after a month of training. If the sentences do not correspond in content to the topic of the Russian language lesson, they can be replaced with equivalent sentences with the same number of letters.

6. Collective complex exercises: repeated reading at the speed of twisting the language, expressive reading with a transition to an unfamiliar part of the text.

a) Many read this way. The teacher sets the same time for all children. After the beginning of a new story is read teacher and understandable to children, they are invited to start reading and continue it for a minute. After a minute, each student noted which word he was able to read. This is followed by a second reading of the same passage. At the same time, the student again notices which words he managed to find, and compares with the first result. The increase in reading speed causes positive emotions in schoolchildren who want to study again.

However, the same passage should not be read more than three times. The next exercise is best organized in the same part - the folds of the tongue.

b) Reading at the speed of twisting the tongue is intended for the development of the articulatory apparatus, therefore there are no requirements for expressiveness. But the requirements for the clarity of pronunciation, the pronunciation of all word endings have been increased. The exercise lasts no more than 30 seconds. After this exercise, reading is carried out according to the same passage, moving on to an unfamiliar part of the text.

c) Reading with a transition to an unfamiliar part of the text. Students are given the task to read the same passage, but with the appropriate speed, expressively. The children read the familiar part to the end and the teacher does not stop them. They move to an unfamiliar part of the text at the same reading speed. Its capabilities will not be enough for a long time, but if you do three exercises every day in reading classes, reading speed will increase over time.

7. The game "Tug".

a) The teacher reads aloud, changing the speed of reading. The students read aloud, trying to catch up with the teacher.

b) the teacher reads aloud, the children to themselves. The teacher stops and the students continue reading.

8. The game "Eagle and tails." The teacher or student begins to read the sentence, the children must quickly find it and continue reading.

9. The game "First and last." Read the first and last letter in a word, the first

and last word in a line, the first and last word in a sentence.

10. A sentence is written on the board, the texts are scattered on the table. In Signal, students search for a given sentence in texts.

11. "Scanning". For 20-30 seconds, students "scan" the text with their eyes in search of important information.

12. Develop a broad outlook.

a) the teacher calls the letter of the alphabet, the child finds this letter with a finger or a pencil and shows it. Practice so that the child remembers where each letter is. Measure the time it takes to find all the letters of the alphabet.

b) look in the center of the table and find all the letters of the alphabet. You cannot move your eyes. The gaze is focused on the center! The child first shows the letter with a pencil, then looks in the center and mentally finds the letter.

c) the child looks only in the middle of the table, tries to see everything, finds the letter "a", then ab, abc, abcg, etc. Each time the speed of finding the previous letters should increase.

An important factor is the "enthusiasm motivation" - in the 1st grade, children study without grades, so grades are very important for them, I put 5 for each additional study; five 5 stars, 5 stars is a reward.

Summary

In conclusion, we can say that reading is a very important process in cognitive activity. A child's ability to read well is the foundation of his success in school. And the point is not only in grades in school subjects, but also in

intellectual development in general.

The better the child learns, the more enthusiastically he does it, the more successful his development, the higher his self-esteem.

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